

Polypropylene Composite for Instrument Panel of Motor Vehicle

H. Kitamura

Plastics Research Department, Kanto-Seiki Co., Ltd., 628 Kumeda Yoshimi-cho, Hiki-gun, Saitama 355-01, Japan

Abstract

High impact resistant composites can be obtained by blending talc powder into some sort of ethylene propylene (E/P) block copolymer made by copolymerization.

Investigating dynamic viscoelasticity of these composites, the maximum value of Loss Modulus (E'') associated with glass transition of ethylene propylene rubber (EPR) shifts to the higher temperature side with the increase of talc blended. This phenomenon enables us to suppose the existence of an affinity between talc and EPR. As a result of observation of the microstructure of the composites by a scanning electron microscope (SEM), we confirmed the existence of EPR adsorbed on the surface of talc particles.

Calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) does not have such an affinity as this, but it can be enclosed in EPR together with polyethylene (PE) component which forms "Domain". This is also very effective to improve impact resistance of PP composites.

INTRODUCTION

The most important functions of the instrument panel of motor vehicle as a panel supporting various instruments are, first, to have enough rigidity to endure severe vibration, second, to have enough impact resistance not to cause serious damage to people in the vehicle at the moment of collision, and then to have enough heat resistance to use it under severely variable temperature.

PP composites have become to be widely used for the instrument panel because of both weight and cost savings at the same time. We have succeeded in developing the PP composite having excellent properties such as high rigidity, high impact resistance and the economy in a very good proportion.

We made clear the scientific reasons why such excellent properties were obtained, by means of morphological observations on the microstructure of such PP composites.

FUNDAMENTAL IDEA IN MATERIAL DESIGN

In order to improve the stiffness and heat resistance, it is effective to blend such inorganic fillers as CaCO_3 or talc powder into PP matrix. However, since it causes the decrease of impact resistance of PP, it is the most serious problem how to prevent such decrease.

From this aspect, our basic idea in material design consists of the absorption mechanism of the impact energy in EPR interface between filler and PP matrix to suppress the crack propagation. This idea is based on the toughening mechanism of E/P block copolymer.

E/P BLOCK COPOLYMER AS A MATRIX

MICROSTRUCTURE OF E/P BLOCK COPOLYMER

E/P block copolymer made by copolymerization is a composition of PP, PE and EPR and does not consist of a typical block structure. According to observation by SEM, PE enclosed with EPR forms "Domains" in PP matrix. (See Fig. 1) The molecular weights of PP matrix have much influence on impact resistance, rigidity, fluidity of E/P block copolymer. Particularly, the contribution to rigidity is great. EPR component acts as an adhesive between PP matrix and PE forming "Domain" and as an energy absorber. Impact resistance varies in accordance with the content and molecular weight of EPR component. PE component enclosed with EPR affects very much on the effect of EPR as energy absorber. Impact resistance and fluidity of E/P block copolymer vary in accordance with the content and molecular weight of PE component.

IMPACT ABSORPTION MECHANISM OF E/P BLOCK COPOLYMER

Adhesion at the interface among three phases mentioned above, and cohesion of EPR and PE have an important relationship to impact resistance. The adhesive strength increases with the increase of the molecular weight of EPR and PE, the surface area of EPR and the molecular entanglement at the interface.

Kuroda and others (2) measured the adhesive strength among PP/EPR/PE three layers. They got a good relationship between Izod Impact and adhesive strength multiplied by PE domain surface area. (See Fig. 2)

They also reported that impact strength was especially high if a fracture initiated in the position as shown in Fig. 3.

Then they concluded that impact energy was absorbed by interface separation between PE and EPR or by voids occurred in PE domain.

HIGH IMPACT RESISTANCE OBTAINED FROM DISPERSION CONTROL OF CALCIUM CARBONATE PARTICLES

The dispersion of CaCO_3 particles are usually dispersed in the matrix as shown in Fig. 4 (A). The particles tend to become the origin of micro cracks caused when impact is applied. However, we can enclose CaCO_3 particles together with PE into EPR by pre-blending CaCO_3 and PE before blending polymer and filler, or by some other special blending methods (5). (See Fig. 5)

In this case, original micro cracks initiated at CaCO_3 particles are held down inside EPR and suppressed to propagate to matrix polymer. Accordingly, high impact resistance of the composite is obtained. (See Fig. 4 (B))

In PP composite filled with CaCO_3 made for experiment, improvement of Izod Impact strength obtained by the special dispersion control is surprising as shown in Table 1.

REINFORCEMENT OF E/P BLOCK COPOLYMER BY FILLING TALC

Talc is generally filled mainly in order to improve flexural modulus. The contribution of talc to the improvement of flexural modulus increases as particle size becomes smaller. (See Fig. 6) Then, we investigated the viscoelastic behavior of special E/P block copolymers filled with some kind of fine talc powder. Dynamic viscoelasticity curve of the composites, being filled with 0 - 40 wt% of talc is shown in Fig. 7.

Values of storage modulus (E') become very high. The maximum value of loss modulus (E'') caused by glass transition of EPR, namely glass transition temperature (T_g) shifts to the higher temperature side. (See Table 2) This means that there exists interaction between filler and matrix polymer. Therefore, we can guess that the mobility of EPR chain decreases due to the adsorption on the surface of filler.

To confirm the function of EPR guessed from results of measurement of dynamic viscoelasticity, we observed by SEM the broken surface of test pieces which were fractured in liquid nitrogen and then etched with xylene. As seen in Fig. 8, we can observe the shadow of EPR existing at the interface between talc particles and PP matrix.

The influences of these unique microstructures on the properties of composite have to be pointed out. Table 3 shows the effect of matrix composition on mechanical properties of composite. The introduction of talc into A type copolymer does not cause so considerable decrease in flow and impact behavior compared with that into B type one. These differences are supposed to be referred to those in chemical affinity mentioned above.

CONCLUSION

Fig. 9 shows a model for microstructure of PP composite stressed on the interface between filler and EPR. From this morphological model, the following points can be suggested.

- (1) EPR improves affinity between PP and filler and causes a good dispersion of filler particles.
- (2) EPR acts as an impact energy absorber.

Since EPR surrounding the dispersed phase makes the adhesion between filler particle and PP matrix stronger, it suppresses initiation of cracks or prevents the cracks occurred from propagating.

Therefore an impact energy absorption mechanism of these filled PP composites is considered to be similar with that of E/P block copolymer.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This report was supported under the considerable cooperation by Dr. Sadao Hoshino, Mr. Osamu Fukui and Mr. Hideho Tanaka of UBE INDUSTRIES, LTD. and Dr. Hiroshi Yui of Mitsubishi Petrochemical Co., Ltd. The author wishes to acknowledge them.

REFERENCES

- 1 T. Kuroda, Kobunshi, 28 (10), 714 (1979)

- 2 T. Kuroda, et al. Polym. Prepr. Japan, 25 (5), 893 (1976)
- 3 O. Fukui, Private Communication on the Structure and Physical Properties of E/P Block Copolymer (Technical Dept. Petrochem. Div. UBE INDUSTRIES, LTD.)
- 4 Technical Report (Mitsubishi Petrochemical Co., Ltd.)
- 5 J.P. Kokai, Sho 57-23642
- 6 Technical Report (UBE INDUSTRIES, LTD.)
- 7 Private Communication (Hirakata Plastics Laboratory, UBE INDUSTRIES, LTD.)

Table 1. Increase of Impact Resistance by Special Dispersion of CaCO_3 (4).

Dispersion type	Izod Impact Strength (-40°C , Notched, Kg. cm/cm)
A E/P block copolymer unfilled	5
B Normal	2
C Special controlled	12
Filler content	20 wt%

Table 2. Tg of EPR vs Content of Talc (7).

Talc content (wt%)	0	10	20	30	40
Tg ($^\circ\text{C}$)	-60	-58	-56	-54	-51

Table 3. Effect of Different E/P Block Copolymer on Mechanical Properties of Composites (6).

	Unit	E/P block copolymer A		E/P block copolymer B	
		Unfilled	20wt% talc	Unfilled	20wt% talc
MFR	g/10 min.	8.6	8.8	7.0	6.0
Izod Impact	Kg. cm/cm	9.7	6.0	13.7	6.8
High Speed Impact	Kg. cm -40°C	392	315	446	274

Fig.1. Microstructure of E/P block copolymer.(1)

Fig.2. Product of true adhesive strength and domain surface area vs Izod Impact strength.(2)

Fig.3. A model showing fracture mechanism of E/P block copolymer.(2)

Fig.4. Morphological model of dispersion and fracture of CaCO_3 filled composite.(4)

Fig.5. SEM photograph of CaCO_3 filled composite with controlled filler dispersion.(5)
 CaCO_3 20 wt%, x 5000

Fig.6. Effect of particle size of talc.(6)

Fig.7. Dynamic viscoelasticity of PP composite filled with talc.(7)

Fig.8. SEM photographs of brittle fractured specimen of talc filled E/P block copolymer. (7)

Talc 10 wt%, x 10000

A CaCO_3 enclosed with PE. (4)

B Talc enclosed with EPR. (7)

Fig.9. Morphological model of CaCO_3 or talc enclosed with PE and EPR.